

**SOCIAL VARIABLES AND SUICIDAL BEHAVIOUR
TENDENCY AMONG UNIVERSITY STUDENTS
IN AKWA IBOM STATE, NIGERIA**

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Abstract:

The study examined social variables and suicidal behaviour tendency among university students in Akwa Ibom State. Two purposes, research questions and hypotheses apiece were formulated to guide the study. The researchers adopted the descriptive survey design. The population of the study comprised all the 5,905 year three undergraduates in the 2 public universities in the state. A sample size of 590 undergraduates was selected through multi-staged sampling procedure. Also, systematic random sampling technique was used to select 10 faculties from the two universities, hence, 59 respondents from each of the sampled faculties were selected using hat and draw method. The researchers self-structured and validated instrument titled "Social Variables and Suicidal Behaviour Tendency among University Students Questionnaire" (SVSBTUSQ) was used for data collection. In order to establish the reliability of the instrument, Cronbach Alpha statistics was applied for test of internal consistency which yielded the reliability co-efficient of .87 and .76. Mean and standard deviation were used in answering the research questions, while Independent t-test was used for testing of hypotheses. Findings of the study showed that suicidal behaviour tendency among university students significantly differ based on estrangement in relationship and family emotionally climate. Conclusion was drawn from the findings and the study recommended among other things that: parents should always maintain emotionally stable and well-adjusted homes where students'

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emotional feelings and needs are adequately addressed to avoid temptation to committing suicide.

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1. Introduction

Suicidal behaviour is currently a social menace affecting the overall wellbeing of students in most public universities. It often occurs in response to overwhelming situations, such as social isolation, death of a loved one, emotional trauma, serious physical illness, aging, unemployment, financial problems, guilty feelings dependence on alcohol or other drugs. The World Health Organization (WHO, 2013), estimated that 800,000 people die by suicide every year, representing an annual suicide rate of 11.4 per 100,000 populations globally and 6.11 per 100,000 populations in developing countries.

Suicidal behaviour is any deliberate action or inaction intended to end one's life in a bid to escape unbearable suffering or to help change adverse conditions of living (Wanyoike 2015). It could be described as, the intentional act of taking one's own life or the destruction of one's own interests or prospects through self-killing. Suicidal behaviour could exert potentially life-threatening consequences, such as taking a drug overdose, deliberately crashing a car, dying by hanging, among others. It often occurs in response to a situation that overwhelms an individual such as social isolation, death of a loved one, emotional trauma, depression as a result of break in relationship, serious illness, aging, unemployment or financial problems feelings of guilt, drug dependence among other (Hudgens, 2003). Suicidal behaviour can be described as fatal and non-fatal suicidal behaviour. Fatal suicidal behaviour refers to completed suicidal behaviour that reflects the person's intent to die and where the person has managed to achieve the pre-determined goal. On the contrary, non-fatal suicidal behaviour is one that does not end the person's life and embodies several manifestations such as those seen in the attempted suicide (Palmer, 2008).

In the past, suicide was regarded as a taboo, disgraceful and families of people who commit suicide were deeply ashamed of themselves. As noted by Alabi, Alabi, Ayinde and Abdulmalik (2015), many families in the past show outright rejection to suicide because of its unexplored psychological burden of feelings of guilt, sorrow and anguish, which are often experienced by the family members and associates of the victims who committed suicide. The authors added that family, friends or acquaintances of people who attempt or commit suicide may feel shock, depression anger and social isolation. In many Nigerian cultures, Ugwuoke (2016) stated that rituals were performed to prevent the spirit of the person that committed suicide from disturbing the living. Some families keep silent about family members who have committed suicide because they may sometimes not want to partake in such rituals that expose any family member as having committed suicide. Many Nigerian cultures do this as a result of the belief system that man is not the author of this life.

However, in this present dispensation, particularly among public Nigerian universities, suicide has continuously become a serious public health and national problem. This is evidence in the rate of suicide cases found among universities students in Nigeria. Ogunseye (2013) found that the incidence of suicide cases had increased over the ten year period spanning 2009-2018, and that the average crude suicide attempt rate was 10-25 per 100,000. The author added that the commonest age group was among teenagers. Chatterjee and Basu (2010) found that suicidal behaviours and their risk factors occur in the same prevalence and frequency for developed and developing countries. Although Nigeria experience paucity of information about the epidemiology of suicide among university students, Nwosu and Odesanmi (2009) found that majority of Nigerian youths including university students committed suicide by the ingestion of Gammalin 20 and use of the locally made guns. Similarly, Offiah and Obiorah (2014) found a total of 11 (47.83%) hanging deaths occurring within the age group of 21-30 years of which the students are not exempted.

2. Theoretical and Conceptual Review Framework

2.1 Hirschi's Theory of Social Bond (1999)

Hirschi (1999) propounded the social bond theory, which states four elements in the social bond between the individual and the society. These include; attachment-which refers to the individual's interest in sensitivity to, and caring for others, as well as concern for the wishes and expectation of other; commitment- which refers to time, energy and effort in pursuing conventional pursuits in our society. If the individual has a stake in the society, then behaving defiantly endangers this; involvement in conventional activities – a person who is involved in conventional activities in the society not only has less desire to engage in suicidal behaviour but he has less time. Finally, the social bond involves belief in the moral validity of the norms established by society for him/her. Those norms must be seen as both good and correct for society and as relevant to our own actions.

This theory is relevant to this study in that it shows the link between family emotional climate and suicidal behaviour tendency of university students. It is understood from the theory that university students who live in a peaceful home environment, who stay close to and live with good and responsible parents would less likely engage in suicidal acts, while those who are neglected and isolated by their parents have increase chances of involving in suicidal actions.

2.2 The Concept of Suicidal Behaviour

Suicidal behaviour is conceptualized differently by various scholars and authors. According to Schneidman (2005), suicidal behaviour is an intentional death, a self-inflicted death which one makes a direct and conscious effort to end one's life. It is the intentional act of taking one's own life or the destruction of one's own interest or prospects. As defined by Alabi, Alabi, Ayinde, and Abdulmalik (2015), suicidal behaviour is the act of killing oneself, deliberately initiated and performed by the person

concerned in the full knowledge or expectation of its total outcome. Maris (2002) also viewed suicidal behaviour as any willful act which is designed to end one's own life. For many, according to him, it is a crime against oneself, nature, humanity and God.

According to Animasahun and Animasahun (2016), suicidal behaviour refers to complex and multi-factorial events with different behavioural characteristics incorporating a range of self-harming acts precipitated by emotional discomfort and distress. Risk factors such as psychological distress, exposure to bullying and violence, parental involvement, and alcohol and illicit drug abuse have been associated with significant increase in the risk for youth suicidal behaviour (Randall, Doku, Wilson and Peltzer, 2014). Therefore, it could be deduced from the definitions that suicidal behaviour is an intentional death, a self-inflicted death which one makes an intentional direct and conscious effort towards putting an end to one's life.

2.3 Estrangement in Relationship and Suicidal Behaviour Tendency among University Students

Friendship is a relationship of mutual affection between two individuals. It is a type of relationship in which people of same sex or opposite sex share similar interests, emotions, feeling and enjoy spending time together. Within the university context, male and female students always receive support from each other and share the most important events of life. The most closest or intimate of relationship is the boyfriend and girlfriend relationship where in most cases, romantic and sexual satisfaction is often cherished. Taking and sharing ideas, opinions, feelings and emotions within the framework of boyfriend and girlfriend relationship bonds are the cornerstone to keeping relationship strong and healthy. If those in friendship relationship experience romantic breakups, Tiffany (2011) noted that such condition may lead to bereavement symptoms such as intrusive thoughts and attempts to suppress them may result in suicide. Romantic breakups often result in the loss of person as a regulator of stimulation and arousal modulation that can lead to psychological trauma. As stated by Davis, Shaver and Vernon (2003) estrangement in relationship may result in romantic breakups, which are often characterized by heart break, sleep disturbances and onset of insomnia being related to ruminations about the lost person.

In a study conducted by Field, Diego, Pelaez, Deeds and Delgado (2009), the authors found that university students who experienced sexual or romantic breakups often tend to have intrusive thoughts, difficulty controlling such intrusive thoughts and insomnia. The authors added that such breakup distress is often accompanied with the urge of committing suicide. Similarly, in a survey of more than 5000 internet respondents including university students, Taylor and Bryant (2007) found that romantic breakups were associated with more extreme physical and emotional distress including exaggerated attempts to re-establish the relationship, angry, vengeful behaviour and attempts to kill oneself, drugs and alcohol use. Fisher, Aron and Brown (2006) also found that young women who are still very much in love but had been rejected by their romantic partner alternatively always view a photograph of their abandoning loved one.

The authors added that the physical, psychological and emotional pains experienced as a result of relationship breakups and romantic rejection often predispose the victims to committing suicide. Losing an attachment figure means losing regulatory control of stable daily patterns, attention, concentration, sleep, food intake and mood, such that they become fragmented, and the individual has a sense of internal disorganization.

Thus, surviving relationship estrangement is one of the most difficult things and the most painful processes in our lives. Losing a romantic partner can make the heart depressed and students on campus who experience such condition may express suicidal thoughts or thoughts of self-harm at the ending of a relationship. The end or dissolution of such illicit romantic relationship is always so distressful and worrisome. More of the non-marital romantic relationship breakups have been linked to increased feelings of depression, decreased self-esteem, particularly for those who were dumped. Baber and Cooper (2011) stated that estrangement in relationship or romantic breakups usually expose the victims to risk of making poor decisions or engaging in risky behaviour such as committing suicide.

2.4 Family Emotional Climate and Suicidal Behaviour Tendency among University Students

Emotional climate of the family refers to the conduciveness and non conduciveness of a home which can make adolescents relate cordially with their parents or run away from them. This implies a psycho-social situation in the home that makes the home attractive or repellent to the children (Travers, 2007). An emotionally conducive home is one in which members of the family are companionable, cooperative, absence of rancor and strife. Under this kind of climate, marital stability is sustained, and attempts are made at meeting the children's needs. Thus, the children from emotionally conducive homes grow up to be emotionally stable and well-adjusted than children from emotionally unconducive homes where friction, discord, hostility and rejection reign. Therefore, to a large extent, parents determine the emotional climate of a family. (Travers, 2007), a child models himself after the pattern of adult world which surrounds him/her. Where emotional trees are missing, the child fails to build up identification with the parents. This becomes the core of a strong and efficient super-ego that acts as a barrier against positive adjustment, and therefore builds a fabric of anti-social behaviours which are not in accordance with societal standards.

Paley, Conger, and Harold (2000) maintained that homes may be characterized as parental acceptance which is characterized by a keen interest and love for members of the family and their activities. Parents are expected to provide warmth in the home which is more crucial and pervasive factor affecting children. Parental acceptance may be expressed in different ways depending on the emotional adjustment of the parents. Emotionally matured parents aim at the development of independence and achievement of goals by children, while the emotionally immature parents attach neurotically to their children and try to mould them to suit desired standards. In other words, emotionally matured parents are more permissive than the immature emotionally parents. When a

child feels accepted, he socializes better, cooperates with others, he is more friendly and cheerful, thereby becoming emotionally stable.

Emotional climate of the family has been associated with the suicidal behaviour among university students. As noted by Okafor and Okafor (2008), young ones who develop undesired negative feelings of isolation due to severe conflicts in the family, may resort to committing suicide. A feeling of isolation may result when one is unable to establish close and meaningful relationship with parents and older role models. A repeatedly unfairly treated, achievements never recognized no matter how hard one tried, love and appreciation withheld are some of the predisposing factors for suicide and suicidal behaviours. Mba (2010) found that young ones who are denied attention or lacks effective relationships with parents, may cultivate feeling of burning resentment and hurt which could predispose such person to doing something wrong. He or she may decide to punish others by punishing him or herself, which may increase the likelihood of suicide.

However, parental attitudes, feelings and actions influence the child and produce in the child lasting identification which, in turn, becomes apparent in the child's perceptions and fantasies of him or herself and others. Okafor and Okafor (2008) observed that when a parent, is violent, the child may wish to escape from the intolerable interactions of his or her parents. As a result, the child may regard his or herself as bad, hostile, destructive, and worthless, which the resultant effect could be committing suicide. This view was supported by Mittendorfer-Rutz, Rasmussen, and Wasserman (2008), who found that a poor family emotional climate is a contributing factor to suicidal behaviours among students.

3. Statement of the Problem

The world over, suicide has become one of the leading causes of death especially in the 15-30 years old age group. The individuals who commit suicide have a motivation to put an end to their depressive conditions. This seems to be very common among university students who are always confronted with unsatisfactory conditions that put those affected at risk for attempted suicide. In most cases, this seems to occur as a result of break in relationship as well as poor emotional climate of the home. The harboured feelings and experiences stored in the mind may result in intense depression and suicide. If depression is not nipped in the bud among students, the rate of suicide may become so alarming, which would be detrimental to national wellbeing.

For instance, in Akwa Ibom State, 27 year old university student named Nsisong Etim of Effiat Ikot Edo Offot Community in Uyo Local Government Area, committed suicide by hanging, presenting a note indicating an intentional ending of his miserable life to escape from constant worries and sufferings resulting from a disrupted family circumstance (Lovina, 2019). This situation and many other cases in Akwa Ibom State seem to be on the increase in recent times and make this study apt.

3.1 Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of the study was to determine how suicidal behaviour tendency among university students differ based on social variables in Akwa Ibom State. Specifically, the study sought to determine how:

- 1) Suicidal behaviour tendency among university students differ based on estrangement in relationship.
- 2) Suicidal behaviour tendency among university students differ based on family emotional climate.

3.2 Research Questions

The following research questions were guided the study:

- 1) What is the difference in suicidal behaviour tendency among university students' based on estrangement in relationship?
- 2) What is the difference in suicidal behaviour tendency among university students' based on family emotional climate?

3.3 Research Hypotheses

The following research hypotheses were guided the study:

- 1) Suicidal behaviour tendency among university students does not significantly differ based on estrangement in relationship.
- 2) Suicidal behaviour tendency among university students does not significantly differ based on family emotional climate.

4. Design of the Study

The study adopted the descriptive survey design. The descriptive survey design is a design which describes the present condition of a particular event. It is a self-report research that enabled a researcher to collect data from respondents through the use of questionnaire. Nworgu (2006) asserted that descriptive survey design is the one in which group of people are studied by collecting and analyzing data from a representative sample of people or items considered for the entire group. The design is suitable for this study as it helped in determining suicidal behaviour tendency among University students differ based on social variables in Akwa Ibom State.

4.1 Population of the Study

The population of the study comprised all the 5,905 year three students in the 2 public Universities in the state. University of Uyo had 4477 (Males 2,092, Females 2,385) students while Akwa Ibom State University had 1428 year three students - Males 612, Females 816 (University of Uyo and Akwa Ibom State University Admission Records Unit, 2019).

4.2 Sample and Sampling Technique

A sample size of 590 undergraduates was selected through multi-staged sampling procedure.

The first stage involved the use of Nwana's (1981) sampling procedure which states that if the population is in many hundred, one needs a sample size of 20%, but if a population is in a few thousands one need a sample size of 10% and for a population of several thousands, a 5% sample or less will be representative of the population. Based on this, the sample size of 590 (10%) was used.

The second stage involved the use of systematic random sampling technique in the selection of 6 out of 12 faculties in University of Uyo; and 4 out of 8 faculties in Akwa Ibom State University, which gave a total 10 faculties. This was done by arranging the faculties numerically from 1 to 12 and 1 to 8, and thereafter, every even-numbered faculty was selected for the study.

The third stage involved the use of hat and draw method in selecting 59 sampled respondents from each of the sampled faculties which gave a total of 590 sampled respondents.

4.3 Instrumentation

The researchers-structured and validated instrument titled "Social Variables and Suicidal Behaviour Tendency among University Students Questionnaire (SVSBTUSQ) were used for data collections. The SVSBTUSQ questionnaire had two sections:

Section A contained the five items each on social variables (estrangement in relationship and family emotional climate).

Section B contained eight items measuring suicidal behaviour tendency among university students. The respondents were requested to give their own opinions or views to the instrument using the symbol (√).

4.4 Validity of the Instrument

The instrument was given to three (3) validators to assess it face validity. Validators were from Sociology of Education and Measurement Evaluation Units of the Department of Educational Foundations, Guidance and Counselling, University of Uyo. The inputs and corrections made by validators were used to form the final copy of the instrument for administration.

4.5 Reliability of the Instrument

To establish the reliability of the instrument, Cronbach Alpha reliability technique was used. Thereafter, the instrument was administered to 40-year 3 university students in a selected department not included in the population sample. The instrument was administered, and data were collated and split into two comparable or equal halves. Data was subjected to correlation and Cronbach Alpha statistic was applied for test of internal consistency of the instrument. This yielded the reliability co-efficient of .87 for social variables items and .76 for items measuring suicidal behaviour tendency among

university students. This index according to Udoh and Joseph (2005) is a high reliability index since the reliability co-efficient is above .50. Therefore, the instrument was deemed reliable for use in the study.

4.6 Method of Data Collection

The instrument was personally administered to the respondents in their respective faculties by the researcher together with two research assistants.

4.7 Method of Data Analysis

Descriptive statistics (mean and standard deviation) was used to answer the research questions, while independent t-test was used to test the research hypotheses at .05 level of significance.

5. Results and Discussion of Findings

Research Question 1: What is the difference in suicidal behaviour tendency among university students based on estrangement in relationship?

Table 1: Mean and standard deviation values of suicidal behaviour tendency among university students based on estrangement in relationship

Variable		n	x	SD
Suicidal Behaviour Tendency Based on Estrangement in Relationship	High Tendency	385	12.83	1.83
	Low Tendency	205	8.03	0.66

Data obtained in Table 1 shows the mean of 12.83 for students with high tendency of suicidal behaviour and 8.03 for students with low tendency of suicidal behaviour. The standard deviation values for high tendency and low tendency are 1.83 and 0.66 respectively. This shows that suicidal behaviour tendency of university students differs based on estrangement in relationship. The inference drawn is that students who experienced breakups or estrangement in relationship have high tendency of suicidal behaviour than those who do not.

Research Question 2: What is the difference in suicidal behaviour tendency among university students based on family emotional climate?

Table 2: Mean and standard deviation values of suicidal behaviour tendency among university students based on family emotional climate

Variable		n	x	SD
Suicidal Behaviour Tendency Based on Family Emotional Climate	High Tendency	340	14.25	2.21
	Low Tendency	250	9.42	1.52

Data obtained in Table 2 shows the mean of 14.25 for students with high tendency of suicidal behaviour and 9.42 for students with low tendency of suicidal behaviour. The

standard deviation values for high tendency and low tendency are 2.21 and 1.52 respectively. This shows that suicidal behaviour tendency of university students differs based on family emotional climate. The inference drawn is that students from homes where unhealthy disagreement, discord, hostility and rejection reigns have high tendency of suicidal behaviour and vice versa.

Hypothesis 1: Suicidal behaviour tendency among university students does not significantly differ based on estrangement in relationship.

Table 3: Summary of independent t-test analysis of Suicidal behaviour tendency among university students based on estrangement in relationship

Variable		n	x	SD	t-cal	t-crit	Decision
Suicidal Behaviour Tendency based on Estrangement in Relationship	High Tendency	385	12.83	1.83	9.1*	1.96	Reject H ₀
	Low Tendency	205	8.03	0.66			

* Significant at P< .05, df = 588; n = 590.

The result on Table 3 indicates that the calculated t-value of 9.1 is greater than the critical t-value of 1.96 at the degree of freedom of 588 and at .05 level of significance. Hence, the null hypothesis is rejected, while the alternate hypothesis is retained. This means that, suicidal behaviour tendency among university students significantly differ based on estrangement in relationship.

Hypothesis 2: Suicidal behaviour tendency among university students does not significantly differ based on family emotional climate.

Table 4: Summary of independent t-test analysis of Suicidal behaviour tendency among university students based on family emotional climate

Variable		n	x	SD	t-cal	t-crit	Decision
Suicidal Behaviour Tendency Based on Family Emotional Climate	High Tendency	340	14.25	2.21	7.21*	1.96	Reject H ₀
	Low Tendency	250	9.42	1.52			

* Significant at P< .05, df = 588; n = 590

The result on Table 4 indicates that the calculated t-value of 7.21 is greater than the critical t-value of 1.96 at the degree of freedom of 588 and at .05 level of significance. Hence, the null hypothesis is rejected, while the alternate hypothesis is retained. This means that, suicidal behaviour tendency among university students significantly differ based on family emotional climate.

6. Discussion of Findings

Result from research hypothesis one showed that suicidal behaviour tendency among university students significantly differ based on estrangement in relationship in Akwa Ibom State. This is in agreement with the findings of the study conducted by Field, Diego, Pelaez, Deeds and Delgado (2009), that university students who experienced sexual or romantic breakups often tend to have intrusive thoughts, difficulty in controlling intrusive thoughts and insomnia. The author added that such breakup distress is often accompanied with the urge of committing suicide. This finding is also in tandem with that of Taylor and Bryant (2007), who found that romantic breakups are associated with more extreme physical and emotional distress including exaggerated attempts to re-establish the relationship, angry, vengeful behaviour as well as and attempts to kill oneself. It is observed from the finding that students who experienced relationship breakups and romantic rejection are most likely to commit suicide than those who do not. Result from research hypothesis two revealed that suicidal behaviour tendency among university students significantly differ based on family emotional climate in Akwa Ibom State. This is in agreement with the findings of the study conducted by Okafor and Okafor (2008), who found that when a parent is violent, the child may wish to escape from the intolerable interactions of his or her parents. As a result, the child may regard his or herself as bad, hostile, destructive, and worthless, which the resultant effect could be committing suicide. This view was supported by Mittendorfer-Rutz, Rasmussen, and Wasserman, (2008), who found that a poor family emotional climate is a contributing factor to suicidal behaviours among students. The above finding suggests that the students' from emotionally stable and well-adjusted and conducive homes are less likely to commit suicide than those from emotionally unstable homes.

7. Conclusion

Based on the findings and discussions, it is therefore concluded that estrangement in relationship and family emotionally climate are significant determinants of students' suicidal behaviour in public universities.

7.1 Recommendation

The following recommendations have been made based on the findings and discussion.

- 1) The University authorities together with their counsellors should always enlighten the students on how to be self-regulated in the absence of an intimate partner and suggest ways of dealing with their academic pursuits and jettison other depression and suicide thought arousals.
- 2) Parents should always maintain emotionally stable and well-adjusted homes where children's emotional feelings and needs are adequately addressed to avoid suicide thoughts.

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